

Identifying Conditions for Hydrogen Sector Coupling Amid Policy Shifts and Rising Electricity Demand

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Abstract

Hydrogen has emerged as an alternative energy carrier used to decarbonize hard-to-electrify sectors and serve as a long-duration energy storage asset for the power sector, however, its deployment depends on technological, policy, and market factors. Using a hydrogen-coupled capacity expansion model, we explore the policy, economic, and demand conditions necessary to support power-to-gas-to-power infrastructure. Our results indicate that, even under optimistic cost and demand scenarios, significant policy support is necessary for hydrogen electrolyzer deployment. Hydrogen fuel cells are only viable under a net-zero constraint, but are limited by the need to meet end-use hydrogen demand, creating competition between hydrogen's different applications. Additionally, while using fuel cells to provide long-duration energy storage can reduce overall capacity requirements for the power sector, the projected growth of large loads, such as data centers, could completely offset sector coupling benefits. Our results elucidate the conditions necessary for large-scale hydrogen deployment and its potential competitiveness.

Hydrogen has emerged as an energy carrier that can be leveraged to decarbonize sectors where direct electrification is not feasible, including buildings, transportation, and industrial processes [1]. Global hydrogen demand is steadily growing and dozens of countries around the world have begun implementing policies to support the development and deployment of its emerging supply chain, including various tax incentives and subsidies across the US and EU [2], resulting in more than 30 MT of new electrolytic hydrogen production capacity being announced in recent years [3].

As countries seek to decarbonize their electricity sectors and grid operators deploy more non-dispatchable renewable energy resources like wind and solar, additional infrastructure is needed to better leverage these resources and mitigate the impacts of their intermittency. The need for long-duration storage, particularly in power systems with high renewable penetration, is well established to leverage seasonally varying resources and reduce system costs [4]. Hydrogen has the potential to fill this need, as it can provide multi-day and seasonal grid balancing for the power sector when produced via electrolysis (Power-to-gas), and be generated and used flexibly, enabling grid operators with broader tools to improve reliability and reduce the overall cost of electricity when used back as electricity (Gas-to-power) [5]. However, prior studies have found that power-to-gas-to-power (P-G-P) systems using hydrogen storage can face significant barriers to their implementation. In particular, the low round-trip efficiency and relatively high costs of gas-to-

power (G-P) infrastructure, such as hydrogen fuel cells, significantly hinder their implementation. Models of highly renewable systems have found that P-G-P deployment is highly sensitive to reductions in cost, providing a potential pathway toward large-scale implementation [6]. Additionally, while the development of hydrogen storage facilities is still in its early stages in the US, early assessments of geologic hydrogen storage suggest that the maximum energy storage capacity exceeds that of natural gas energy storage [7], indicating strong potential for P-G-P systems if existing barriers can be overcome.

While there has been significant interest and plans to deploy hydrogen infrastructure in the US, the scale of the hydrogen economy is far from certain. Hundreds of projects have been announced in the past several years, but very few have been completed on schedule [8]. Additionally, cost estimates for hydrogen technologies are highly uncertain, with recent projections indicating greater costs than previously anticipated [3]. Moreover, while multiple studies have established the need for policy support to drive the buildout of the hydrogen economy, these policies vary significantly in both their expected efficacy and where they are implemented. In the US, there is significant uncertainty about the longevity of existing tax incentives and whether new incentives will be introduced in the future [9]. Similarly, it is still unclear to what extent hydrogen end-use technologies will penetrate various sectors, as demand for hydrogen remains concentrated in the industrial sector [3]. In the absence of significant demand growth, it may become difficult for stakeholders to justify further investment in improving and deploying these technologies.

Despite these uncertainties, rapid and large-scale investment in hydrogen could be critical for countries to meet their stated climate targets, especially in end-use sectors where hydrogen use is either unavoidable or highly competitive, such as industry (e.g., steel and chemical feedstock) and long-haul transport [10], [11], [12]. Beyond those critical cases, there are a myriad of other sectors where hydrogen may become competitive and have limited use (e.g., light-duty vehicles, commercial heating, aviation, etc.), but their pathways are far less certain. In light of this, it is essential to understand the infrastructure requirements to meet hydrogen demand under a range of conditions that reflect possible future pathways. Furthermore, to comprehensively map out intersectoral dynamics and guide proper systems planning, models of hydrogen electrolysis and the broader supply chain must also be paired with models of regional power systems.

The interactions between hydrogen and power systems are well-studied in existing literature [13], [14], [15], [16], [17]. Prior work demonstrates the ability to leverage hydrogen electrolysis as a flexible demand source for electricity to reduce curtailment, electricity costs, and battery storage and transmission requirements [18], [19]. However, few studies explore the potential impacts of using hydrogen to meet end-use demand and function as a long-duration storage asset simultaneously, enabling policies, and the resulting impacts on grid operations and infrastructure needs. Studies of Texas, for example, include technology options for G-P infrastructure in addition to modeling end-use demand, but different conditions are not explored to understand when G-P infrastructure is feasible or necessary [20], [21]. A study of New England identified significant benefits of electrolytic hydrogen as a flexible demand source and although it found that G-P infrastructure had limited use cases, the study considered a limited set of demand and policy scenarios, and the region of analysis had limited potential for underground hydrogen storage,

further limiting the broad dynamics [22]. Moreover, none of the existing analyses of hydrogen deployment reflect the current scale of projected electricity demand as a result of data centers and large-load growth, which will have compounding impacts on infrastructure requirements in the power sector [23], [24], [25]. Furthermore, existing models that demonstrate the use of P-G-P infrastructure tend to do so in either zero-emission or highly renewable systems, which may not reflect the enabling conditions to deploy these technologies in the absence of strict carbon policies, particularly for the US and similar countries. Thus, there is a need to understand to what extent these two roles of hydrogen – as both a long-duration storage asset and an energy carrier for various end-uses – synergize and compete with each other in existing systems given ongoing shifts in policy and demand.

To address these gaps, we model the Texas Interconnection, an isolated grid that represents both the largest hydrogen generation hub and fastest data center growth region in the US, and co-optimize the power sector and the hydrogen supply chain through 2050. We test this model with a suite of economic, policy, and demand scenarios to reflect the uncertain future for the hydrogen economy. Through this, we elucidate (1) the necessary conditions for electrolytic hydrogen to be leveraged to meet end-use demand, (2) the extent to which hydrogen can simultaneously serve as a long-duration storage asset for the power sector while meeting end-use demand, (3) the infrastructure requirements in the power sector to support this new supply chain, and (4) how the interactions of these two sectors influence and drive investment decisions. Understanding and quantifying these interactions are critical for identifying the necessary steps to develop the hydrogen supply chain in its early stages and clarifying the expected impacts on a rapidly evolving electricity sector.

Scenarios Overview

For this analysis, we capture uncertainties in hydrogen demand, policy and regulatory frameworks, and capital costs associated with hydrogen technologies by assessing 512 scenarios. The scenarios, described in Table 1, incorporate four different hydrogen demand projections from 2025–2050, spanning current demand, industrial demand, transportation demand, and a combined case that includes both industrial and transportation demand (Supplemental Figure S1). Policy scenarios reflect various approaches to facilitate decarbonization: an incentive scenario extending clean energy and hydrogen tax credits from the Inflation Reduction Act through 2050, a \$100/ton of CO₂ carbon tax scenario informed by previous studies demonstrating its impact in driving significant shifts in resource portfolios in Texas’ hydrogen and power sectors [20], a net-zero emissions pathway with 50% reduction by 2035 and complete decarbonization by 2050, and a no-policy baseline reflecting current federal and state level uncertainty. For each demand-policy combination, capital costs of fuel cells and electrolyzers are varied between 25% and 100% of current projections. Additionally, two electricity demand trajectories are analyzed: a business-as-usual (BAU) through 2050, and one incorporating short-term load growth driven by emerging large loads, such as data centers.

Table 1: Overview of the parameters modeled across combined scenarios.

Parameter	Sub-scenarios	Values/Ranges
Electricity demand	Without large loads	716 TWh in 2050

	With large loads	1519 TWh in 2050
Hydrogen demand	Current demand	3.6 MMT in 2025; 3.6 MMT in 2050
	Industrial demand	3.6 MMT in 2025; 6 MMT in 2050
	Transportation demand	0 MMT in 2025, 3.8 MMT in 2050
	Industrial and transportation demand	3.6 MMT in 2025; 9.8 MMT in 2050
Policy	No policy	No present or future policies
	Extended tax credits	Power: 30% investment tax credit; \$27.5/MWh production tax credit Hydrogen: \$3/kg for electrolyzers, \$0.60/kg for SMR with CCS
	Carbon Tax	\$100/ton CO ₂
	Net-zero	50% emission reduction by 2035, 100% by 2050
Infrastructure Costs	Electrolyzer CAPEX	BAU, -25%, -50%, and -75%
	Fuel Cell CAPEX	BAU, -25%, -50%, and -75%

Policies and end-use demand are key determinants of P-G-P growth

Our findings indicate that significant policy intervention is necessary to support widespread adoption of P-G-P infrastructure. In the absence of any policy interventions or additional growth in hydrogen demand relative to present day, electrolytic hydrogen production is sufficient to meet all hydrogen demand in 2050. However, when new demand for hydrogen is introduced, steam methane reformation (SMR) plants constitute 42-78% of total installed hydrogen production capacity, even when electrolyzer costs are reduced by 75% (Figure 1a). Introducing policy interventions, such as tax credits or a carbon tax, results in greater electrolyzer build-out under transportation demand scenarios, where peak demand hours more closely align with peak renewable generation, coinciding with hydrogen production times (Figure 1b). In these cases, extending the Inflation Reduction Act credits is enough to completely eliminate SMR capacity by 2050. Notably, despite also being eligible for tax credits from the Inflation Reduction Act, there is no scenario where SMR plants with carbon capture and storage (CCS) capabilities are installed. Conversely, in industrial and combined demand scenarios, where there is a base demand for hydrogen at all hours, a complete phase out of SMR only occurs under a net-zero emissions constraint. These results suggest that different end-use demands for hydrogen necessitate different policy interventions to encourage green hydrogen production or to foster more flexible hydrogen demand to better leverage renewable resources.

Figure 1: Heatmaps showing the installed capacity in 2050 for all demand, policy, and hydrogen demand scenarios for (a) SMR plants, (b) electrolyzers, (c) fuel cells, and (d) hydrogen storage.

Although variations in electrolyzer costs and hydrogen demand induce modest increases in electrolyzer capacity, fuel cell (Figure 1c) and hydrogen storage (Figure 1d) capacity exhibit limited sensitivity to these factors, and their installed capacities are minimal without policy intervention. Implementing tax credits or a carbon tax increases the capacity for both electrolyzers and hydrogen storage; however, fuel cell capacity remains near zero under these same policies except in specific demand scenarios. Notably, when a carbon tax is applied, the greatest deployment of G-P infrastructure occurs when only hydrogen demand from the transportation sector is considered. Unlike other demand profiles, hydrogen demand for transportation has a strong diurnal pattern, with periods of near-zero demand during portions of the day (Supplemental Figure S2). The gaps in demand enable the power sector to use hydrogen more frequently for other purposes, like energy storage, whereas other demand scenarios maintain a near-constant demand for hydrogen due to industrial needs and have minimal fuel cell deployment. This indicates that, while end-use hydrogen demand drives electrolyzer adoption, it also limits hydrogen availability for conversion to electricity for long-duration energy storage.

This behavior is also reflected in the net-zero policy scenarios, where electrolyzers, fuel cells, and storage technologies reach their peak capacities. In these scenarios, electrolyzers and hydrogen storage capacities increase alongside annual hydrogen demand. Additionally, hydrogen storage capacity tends to increase with reductions in fuel cell capital costs in a net-zero scenario, whereas in less stringent policy scenarios, it is more sensitive to changes in electrolyzer costs. In contrast,

installed fuel cell capacity is the greatest in net-zero scenarios with low end-use hydrogen demand, indicating that competition between different hydrogen uses will limit the use of G-P infrastructure to provide electricity to the power sector. Still, we observe that fuel cell capacity in high-demand scenarios increases as electrolyzer capital costs decrease, implying that increased P-G capacity allows for additional hydrogen production for energy storage.

H₂ storage addresses seasonal renewable energy availability and end-use needs

The hourly hydrogen storage profile for the system in 2050 reveals seasonal cycling patterns (Figure 2a). Charging and discharging of hydrogen storage directly correlate with wind and solar resources availability throughout the year (Supplemental Figure S3). Significant amounts of hydrogen are stored from March through July when renewable energy resources, particularly wind, have their highest hourly capacity factors on average. This stored hydrogen then tends to be used in late summer and early winter when wind resources are at their lowest. This behavior is consistent across demand, policy, and cost scenarios, and primarily varies only in magnitude. While fuel cells are dispatched during these periods, they are only used for a few hours or a few days at a time (Figure 2b). Outside of these brief periods of fuel cell utilization, this sustained consumption of stored hydrogen in the fall and winter is to address gaps in hydrogen supply to meet end-use demand, rather than for seasonal storage.

Figure 2: Seasonal hydrogen storage is primarily governed by gaps in renewable generation in order to meet end-use hydrogen demand. (a) The amount of hydrogen stored in each modeled hour in 2050 for all scenarios and (b) Fuel cell dispatch in each modeled hour in 2050 for all scenarios.

Fuel cells are used more frequently and at higher outputs in low-demand scenarios compared to high-demand ones under identical policy and cost assumptions. Only 56% of scenarios dispatched fuel cells at any point in 2050, and only 33% dispatched fuel cells for more than 24 hours in total throughout the year (Figure 3a). All of the scenarios with the highest fuel cell utilization occur under a net zero constraint, with a significant decline in cases where less strict policies are enforced. When these fuel cells are dispatched, they tend to operate at or near their maximum capacity (Figure 3b), with limited instances of lower utilization rates. These findings indicate that

end-use demand is a primary driver for hydrogen storage and electrolyzer adoption, whereas energy storage for the power sector remains a secondary application when excess hydrogen is available. However, this secondary application only occurs under net-zero conditions, suggesting that future fuel cell usage will be nearly non-existent in the absence of strict policy interventions.

Figure 3: Fuel cell dispatch is limited to peak periods and are almost exclusively used in net-zero conditions. (a) Number of hours in 2050 where fuel cells are dispatched across all scenarios. (a) Sorted dispatch curve for hydrogen fuel cells in 2050 in each scenario. Color-coded are net-zero policies with reduced electrolyzer and fuel cell costs (-75%) across demand instances: combined (green), transportation (blue), industrial (yellow), and current (red). All other scenarios are shown in grey.

Large-load growth offsets capacity reductions from H₂ sector coupling

Although fuel cell use remains limited across all scenarios, it can still significantly impact the power sector. As fuel cell and electrolyzer costs decline and installed P-G-P capacity increases, significant shifts in electricity generation and storage capacity can be expected, depending on the projected electricity demand (Figure 4a). Both with and without large electric loads, an increase in P-G-P capacity primarily leads to higher wind and solar capacities for the no policy, tax incentive, and carbon tax scenarios, with small reductions in thermal generation capacity in some instances. Under a net-zero policy constraint, however, increasing P-G-P infrastructure results in power

system capacity reductions across all hydrogen demand scenarios when excluding large loads. Notably, solar and battery power capacities tend to decline as increased P-G-P capacity, particularly fuel cells, enables better wind resource utilization throughout the year, reducing the need to overbuild solar capacity to meet peak demand in the summer. This suggests that increasing P-G-P deployment in net-zero or highly renewable systems can allow for more efficient use of grid resources and reduce system capacity overall.

However, when electricity demand from large loads is modeled, this trend is reversed, and we observe net increases in renewable energy capacity when significant amounts of P-G-P capacity are deployed. The need for renewable generation to satisfy both hydrogen and electricity demand from large loads, due to the net-zero requirement, largely offsets any capacity reductions from hydrogen sector coupling. While total system capacity often is approximately the same or increases in net-zero instances where large-loads are modeled, there is a significant reduction in dispatchable thermal generation capacity, particularly nuclear. Moreover, the total system capacity decreases when both industrial and transportation hydrogen demand are modeled, suggesting that a sufficiently large hydrogen supply chain could still reduce power sector capacity. Notably, this behavior only occurs in net-zero instances. Scenarios that model other policy assumptions show that large-load growth has little to no impact on capacity shifts due to hydrogen sector coupling. Nevertheless, these findings underscore that, despite the recognized potential of hydrogen supply chains, the benefits and system capacity shifts are highly dependent on the regional power sector characteristics and local electricity needs.

Figure 4: P-G-P infrastructure can lead to significant capacity reductions in the power sector, but is dependent on the projected electricity demand. The bar plots show the changes in electricity generation and storage capacity when fuel cell and electrolyzer costs are reduced by 75% relative to BAU cost projections, thereby increasing P-G-P deployment, when (a) emerging large loads are excluded from the model and (b) when large loads are included.

Expansion pathways are robust across scenarios

The distribution of installed wind and solar capacity is consistent in most regions across different demand and policy instances (Figure 5). Wind and solar capacity are predominantly concentrated in the Permian Basin (N, W, FW in Figure 5a), where the highest quality wind and solar resources are available. As expected, renewable capacity in these regions increases significantly in response to the policies modeled in this work. As a result, transmission expansion centers around two primary corridors that connect resources in the Panhandle (PH) and Permian Basin to demand centers in the east. Additional policies also incentivize the utilization of lower-quality resources

closer to demand centers, particularly for solar infrastructure, which is less limited by land-use constraints than wind farms. Meanwhile, we find that, on average, there are minimal changes in the spatial distribution and quantity of renewable energy infrastructure in response to changes in hydrogen demand, except in specific load zones, such as the North load zone for wind capacity. One notable exception is the significant increase in wind capacity in the Texas Panhandle, a region characterized by the highest quality wind resources. This increase also corresponds with an increase in electrolyzer capacity in the same region, suggesting that increasing hydrogen demand could justify the development of renewable resources in regions remote from population and demand centers.

Figure 5: Electricity and hydrogen capacity spatial distributions are consistent across demand and policy assumptions. (a) Map of installed capacity in the power sector in a net-zero scenario with both industrial and hydrogen demand, demand from large loads, and BAU cost projections for electrolyzers and fuel cells. (b) Map of installed capacity in the hydrogen supply chain for the same scenario. (c) Box plots showing the distribution of electricity and hydrogen capacity across the nine load zones in this model broken down by policy. (d) Box plots showing the distribution of capacity across all scenarios broken down by hydrogen demand.

Hydrogen electrolyzers are primarily co-located with the highest-quality renewable resources in the Permian Basin and Panhandle. Despite minimal changes in wind and solar capacity with increased hydrogen demand, resource utilization in these regions shifts toward prioritizing hydrogen production over meeting electricity demand. Notably, this behavior is partially driven by the hourly matching and geographical matching constraints imposed in the model. Relaxing these constraints may lead to a different distribution of hydrogen infrastructure (i.e., sited closer to hydrogen demand centers), but they are also necessary to ensure that grid-connected electrolyzers are being powered by renewable electricity. Additionally, while there are small amounts of electrolyzer capacity near urban demand centers in ‘No Policy’ instances, introducing new policies causes that capacity to shift out to the Permian Basin as well. But, unlike electrolyzers, hydrogen fuel cells and hydrogen storage are predominantly located near hydrogen demand centers and are consistent across different demand and policy assumptions. Thus, hydrogen is transported via pipelines and stored in geological formations until used for end-use demand, or converted back to electricity. While transportation demand seems to be a more significant driver for fuel cell adoption, as discussed previously, hydrogen storage capacity is more strongly associated with scenarios where industrial hydrogen demand is considered.

Hydrogen storage capacity requirements tend to be well aligned with existing natural gas infrastructure. Median installed capacity for underground storage across all scenarios is the greatest in the Coast load zone along the Gulf Coast and is nearly double the capacity of the next highest load zone (Figure 6). This region is also where the majority of existing natural gas facilities in the state are concentrated, including both salt caverns and depleted oil and gas reservoirs. Additionally, the total working gas capacity of these storage facilities is higher than the underground hydrogen storage requirements across all scenarios. Based on this, the infrastructure needs for the hydrogen supply chain tend to be well-aligned with existing natural gas infrastructure across scenarios. Thus, these facilities can potentially be utilized to support the deployment of hydrogen infrastructure both in the short-term by blending hydrogen with natural gas and in the long-term by potentially converting some or all of these facilities into pure hydrogen storage.

Figure 6: Resulting hydrogen storage needs are well-aligned with existing natural gas storage. A map of the nine modeled load zones where each load zone is colored based on the median installed underground hydrogen storage capacity across all scenarios. The blue circles show the location and working gas capacity of existing salt caverns and depleted oil and reservoirs currently used for natural gas storage in Texas.

Discussion

By developing a case study in Texas, a region characterized by high renewable energy resources, growing electricity demand, and an existing demand base for hydrogen, we evaluate the likely early – and sustained – buildout of the electrolytic hydrogen supply chain, and draw insights for regions and countries with similar attributes or trajectories. The spatial distribution of infrastructure appears to be consistent across demand and policy scenarios, suggesting that regions where high-quality renewable resources should be prioritized and leveraged for electrolytic hydrogen production, while storage facilities and G-P capacity are optimally sited in proximity to regions with high electricity and hydrogen demand. This pathway necessitates significant investment in pure hydrogen pipelines, as existing natural gas infrastructure would require significant retrofits to be able to transport large volumes of hydrogen. Furthermore, our findings indicate that, while policies to stimulate end-use hydrogen demand are necessary, demand growth alone, without additional policy support, is unlikely to result in significant P-G-P investment.

While these findings suggest that CCS may play a limited role in future hydrogen systems, this conclusion may be influenced by the absence of a comprehensive CO₂ network representation within the model. Prior research has demonstrated the cost-saving benefits of carbon capture and transport in decarbonized systems, suggesting that their potential contribution to the hydrogen supply chain may be understated in this work [26]. Moreover, this study does not account for the broader hydrogen supply chain in the US or the effects of imports and exports on hydrogen use in Texas. Although international studies have shown that imported hydrogen can support peak demand periods in the power sector, Texas' anticipated role as a hydrogen exporter is likely to further increase regional capacity requirements and constrain hydrogen availability for grid balancing purposes in the region's power system [13], [27].

Lastly, while hydrogen sector coupling is necessary for achieving deep decarbonization, the potential benefits to the power sector may be limited. Stringent net-zero requirements or similar policies are necessary to effectively deploy and utilize P-G-P infrastructure for long-duration energy storage. These policy efforts must be accompanied by a substantial increase in hydrogen demand to justify further investments in the supply chain. However, doing so risks limiting the system's seasonal grid balancing capabilities. Developing strategies to enhance hydrogen demand flexibility, such as load shifting or curtailment, could facilitate the deployment of G-P infrastructure while preserving a robust hydrogen market. Furthermore, the anticipated benefits of hydrogen sector coupling, such as reductions in generation capacity and overall system costs, remain uncertain and are highly dependent on the power system's conditions. Continued growth in electricity demand, whether driven by large loads or other demand sources, could diminish or entirely negate the potential benefits of P-G-P infrastructure.

Methods

Optimization Model

For this analysis, we use SWITCH, an open-source capacity expansion model to guide long-term grid planning decisions [28] that has been used to analyze power systems with high renewable penetration in regions all over the world, including Texas [29], [30], [31]. The version of SWITCH used in this analysis (SWITCH-ERCOT) has been developed to model the Texas Interconnection and expanded to include a representation of the hydrogen supply chain to support the modeling of a variety of hydrogen production, storage, and transport technologies. Here, we reproduce key equations and constraints from the SWITCH model documentation as well as information related to representation of the hydrogen supply chain, but additional details are available in the Supplemental Materials and in the documentation for the SWITCH model [28].

SWITCH-ERCOT evaluates investment and operational decisions over the specified time horizon with perfect foresight to determine the least-cost optimal set of infrastructure to meet both electricity and hydrogen demand. Investments and operation decisions are made to minimize the total sum of investment and operation costs, as shown in Equation 1.

$$\min \sum_{p \in P} d_p \left\{ \sum_{c^f \in C^{fixed}} c_p^f + \sum_{t \in T_p} w_t^{year} \sum_{c^v \in C^{var}} c_t^v \right\} \quad (1)$$

Where C^{fixed} is the set of fixed costs in each investment period p , which includes both the fixed operation costs and the annualized capital expenditures. C^{var} is the set of the variable costs (e.g., variable operating costs, fuel costs, etc.) which are then multiplied by a weighting factor w_t^{year} to scale the costs in the representative time points up to the full investment period. The costs in each investment are then converted into a net present value using a discount factor, d_p . Other governing equations for the power sector and the hydrogen supply chain are represented using the same zonal system for ERCOT and have identical formulations. Investments in new generation, storage, and transmission capacity are represented as continuous variables for each load zone and investment period. Some technologies, such as wind and solar, have a limit to their installed capacity in a load zone based on the availability of resources (Equations 2-3). Given the temporal resolution of this model, unit commitment and ramping rates are not considered in the operational representation in this analysis. Thus, dispatch of power system and hydrogen infrastructure is only constrained by the installed capacity in an investment period and any relevant derating factors, such as outage factors or capacity factors for renewable resources (Equation 4).

$$K_{g,p}^G = \sum_{p' \in P_{g,p}^{on}} B_{g,p'}^G \quad \forall g \in G, \forall p \in P \cup \{p_0\} \quad (2)$$

$$0 \leq K_{g,p}^G \leq \overline{k}_g^G \quad \forall g \in G, p \in P \quad (3)$$

$$0 \leq P_{g,t} \leq \eta_g \eta_{g,t} K_{g,p(t)}^G \quad \forall g \in G, \forall t \in T_g^{on} \quad (4)$$

Where the installed capacity $K_{g,p}^G$ is the sum of the installed capacity ($B_{g,p'}^G$) in current and prior periods as well as pre-existing capacity after accounting for retirements, \overline{k}_g^G is the maximum amount of installed capacity for a technology (g), $P_{g,t}$ is the dispatch of a technology at a specific timepoint (t), and all derating factors are represented by η . In the case of storage capacity, investment decisions are made for power and energy capacity separately. The storage level for a given technology is constrained by the installed energy storage capacity and injections and withdrawals are governed by installed power capacity (Equations 5-6). Storage level is tracked across timepoints using Equation 7.

$$0 \leq C_{g,t}^S \leq r_g^{max} \overline{P}_{g,t} \quad \forall g \in G^S, t \in T_g^{on} \quad (5)$$

$$0 \leq Z_{g,t}^S \leq K_{g,p}^S \quad \forall g \in G^S, t \in T_g^{on} \quad (6)$$

$$Z_{g,t}^S = Z_{g,t-1}^S + (\eta_g^S C_{g,t}^S - P_{g,t}) \Delta_t^T \quad \forall g \in G^S, t \in T_g^{on} \quad (7)$$

Where $C_{g,t}^S$ represents the amount of energy a storage project stores in a timepoint and is constrained by the maximum the discharge ($\overline{P}_{g,t}$) multiplied by an optional parameter to fix the charge to discharge ratio (r_g^{max}). $Z_{g,t}^S$ is the total amount of energy stored by a storage project in a timepoint, $Z_{g,t-1}^S$ is the amount of energy stored in the prior timepoint, η_g^S is the roundtrip efficiency of the storage project and is applied when the project is charged, and Δ_t^T is the length of

the timepoint in hours to convert the net charge or discharge from power (MW) to energy (MWh). Electricity and hydrogen flow between load zones are represented using a simplified bulk transport model, where existing transmission lines and pipelines are aggregated in singular corridors between zones (Equations 8-9).

$$K_{l,p}^L = b_l^L + \sum_{p':(l,p') \in LB \text{ and } p' \leq p} B_{l,p'}^L \quad \forall l \in L, \forall p \in P \quad (8)$$

$$0 \leq F_{z,z',t} \leq \eta_{l(z,z')}^L K_{l(z,z'),p} \quad \forall (z, z') \in L^D, \forall p \in P, \forall t \in T_p \quad (9)$$

Where $K_{l,p}^L$ is the total installed capacity in a transmission corridor, b_l^L is the pre-existing capacity, $B_{l,p'}^L$ is the installed capacity in an investment period, $\eta_{l(z,z')}^L$ is a derating factor for a corridor to reflect outages, and $F_{z,z',t}$ is the power or hydrogen flow through a specific corridor in a timepoint. Operational decisions for dispatching generation, charging and discharging storage projects, and transmission flows, are combined into an energy balance equation along with electricity and hydrogen demand to ensure that energy demand is being met during all modeled timepoints (Equation 10)

$$\sum_{p^i \in P^{inject}} p_{z,t}^i = \sum_{p^w \in P^{withdraw}} p_{z,t}^w \quad \forall z \in Z, \forall t \in T \quad (10)$$

Where P^{inject} represents that all injections of electricity or hydrogen into a load zone at a specific time, including generation dispatch, storage discharging, and transmission flow into a load zone. Conversely, $P^{withdraw}$ reflects all electricity and hydrogen withdrawals, including storage charging, transmission flow out of a load zone, and electricity and hydrogen demand at each timepoint. Lastly, we impose additionality, geographical matching, and temporal matching constraints on electrolytic hydrogen production to ensure that hydrogen production is matched by renewable electricity generation in the same hour and region (Equation 11). These constraints are consistent with previous federal guidelines for eligibility for the clean hydrogen tax credit [32]. Moreover, since we only consider grid-connected electrolyzers in this model, such operational constraints are necessary to mitigate the increased emissions associated from using grid electricity for hydrogen production [33].

$$\sum_{h \in H_z} \frac{P_{h,t}}{\eta_h} \leq \sum_{g \in G_z^R} P_{g,t} \quad \forall z \in Z, \forall t \in T \quad (11)$$

Where $P_{h,t}$ is the dispatch of a hydrogen electrolysis facility in load zone z at timepoint t , and η_h is the efficiency of the hydrogen project in units of (kg/h)/MW. SWITCH-ERCOT is implemented in Python using the Pyomo modeling framework and solved using the Gurobi solver.

Case Study and Input Data

We apply SWITCH-ERCOT to a nine-region model of the Texas Interconnection. The region is modeled in five-year investment periods from 2025 to 2050. For each period, we model an entire year in four-hour increments to ensure we can represent the behavior of long-duration energy

storage while still achieving computational tractability [34]. We identify existing generation assets, their nameplate capacities, and relevant operational parameters from EIA Form 860 [35]. Additionally, to reflect the rapid growth of solar and batteries installations in this region, we include planned projects from the interconnection queue that are highly likely to be connected based on ERCOT reports on current and planned resource capacity [36]. New generation capacity options are represented as distinct technologies rather than individual plants. Each candidate technology is available in each load zone, except for geothermal which is only available in areas with sufficient resources [37]. By default, each technology is available for installation in each investment period. However, since construction and installation times are not explicitly modeled for new capacity installations, we constrain new nuclear capacity to not be available until 2030 to account for extended construction times and possible delays. Investment and operational cost data for the candidate technologies in the electricity sector are obtained from the 2023 Annual Technology Baseline [38]. Relevant operational parameters for candidate technologies are assumed to be the same as those in the ATB. Additionally, fuel cost projections are obtained from the 2022 Annual Energy Outlook [39].

We leverage historical hourly generation data from ERCOT to develop capacity factor profiles for all existing wind and solar generation capacity [40]. Capacity factors for candidate wind and solar projects are estimated using the National Solar Radiation Database and Wind Integration Toolkit [41], [42]. All resource profiles assume the same technological parameters and reference years and were selected based on which resource profiles most closely resembled historical data for existing projects in each load zone. Resources are then grouped into low, medium, and high-quality resources based on their average annual capacity factors. Each set of resources is available as a separate technology option in each load zone and constrained by the amount of land available [43].

Hourly electricity demand is obtained from ERCOT's 2024 Long Term Load Forecasts (LTLF) for eight of the load zones represented in this model [44]. Load forecasts are not available for the Texas Panhandle, but due to the sparse population and lack of industry, we assume a load of zero for all modeled hours for this load zone. The 2024 LTLF estimates a rapid growth in electricity projections due to emerging large loads, such as data centers, resulting in annual energy consumption growing from roughly 500 TWh in 2024 to 1125 TWh in 2033 (Supplemental Figure S4). Beyond 2033, we make no future assumptions about additional large load growth and assume an annual growth rate of 1.78% from 2033 to 2050, which is the average annual growth rate of non-large loads in the 2024 LTLF. We assume consistent percent growth across all load zones from 2033 to 2050. To understand the impacts of large loads on hydrogen sector coupling, we also model the ERCOT system without large loads and assume the same 1.78% annual growth rate.

For the hydrogen supply chain, we include both proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzers and steam methane reformation (SMR) with and without carbon capture as hydrogen production options. Capital costs for electrolyzers are derived from long-term forecasts from the International Energy Agency [45] and we assume a 66% efficiency for all investment periods [46]. Fixed operational costs are assumed to be 3% of the capital costs and, while the buying and selling of electricity are not explicitly modeled in SWITCH-ERCOT, we assign a variable O&M cost to electrolyzers based on the historical industrial electricity prices in Texas [47] as well as water

consumption [48]. SMR plants are assumed to be mature technologies with minimal cost reductions, so we assume present-day costs for the full time horizon of the model [21]. For SMR with CCS, we assume only the investment cost of carbon capture infrastructure declines over time and we assume a capture rate of 90% [21]. Fuel cells and hydrogen combustion turbines are available as gas-to-power infrastructure. Fuel cells costs are derived based on existed costs and expected technology learning curves [49], while hydrogen combustion turbines are only available in 2050 and use expected future costs [6]. Given the prevalence of geological formations in Texas, including both depleted reservoirs and salt caverns, we do not impose any geographic constraints on underground hydrogen storage capacity [7], [50].

Existing natural gas pipelines are used as an option for hydrogen transport. Inter-zonal pipelines are identified based on geographical data from the Texas Railroad Commission (TRC) [51]. While detailed information about each individual line is not available, hourly gas flow limits are estimated for each corridor using the Weymouth equation based on typical geometric properties and expected operating conditions based on TRC data. While studies estimate that hydrogen can be blending at up to a 20% ratio with natural gas, we assume a conservative maximum hydrogen blending rate of 5% for existing pipelines in Texas [52]. In addition, we have the option to construct new, pure hydrogen pipelines between adjacent load zones based on estimated transport costs [53].

For the different scenarios for end-use hydrogen demand, we estimate annual demand based on the maximum expected potential for hydrogen in the state for transportation and industrial sectors [27]. For the “Current”, “Industrial”, and “Combined” sub-scenarios, we assume demand in 2025 is equivalent to present day demand for hydrogen in the industrial sector, which is approximately 3.6 MMT. In scenarios where “Transportation” demand projection is used, we assume there is no initial demand for hydrogen. Then, we assume the maximum potential demand for hydrogen in an end-use sector occurs in 2050, which corresponds to 6 MMT for industrial, 3.8 MMT for transportation, and 9.8 MMT in the combined case. Annual demands are then converted into hourly profiles using existing industrial load data and refueling behavior for fuel cell electric vehicles [54], [55]. We assume these profiles are the same for all investment periods and scale them up proportionally to the projected annual demand for that sector. State-wide transportation demand for hydrogen is then distributed across the nine load zones based on the number of existing vehicles registrations in each region. Industrial demand is distributed proportionally based on existing demand for natural gas [47].

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